
University St. Kliment Ohridski Bitola
Faculty of Tourism and Hospitality Ohrid

Conference Proceedings INSCOSES
XVII International Scientific Conference on Services Sector
INSCOSES, Ohrid, 26-27 September 2024

CIP - Каталогизација во публикација
Национална и универзитетска библиотека "Св. Климент Охридски",
Скопје

338.48(062)

33(062)

338.47(062)

640.4(062)

INTERNATIONAL Scientific Conference on Service sector INSCOSES (17 ;
2024 ; Ohrid)

Conference Proceedings INSCOSES ; XVII International Scientific
Conference on Service sector INSCOSES, Ohrid, 26-27 September 2024
[Електронски извор] / [organizing committee Aleksandar Trajkov ... и
др.]. - Текст во PDF формат, содржи 435 стр., илустр. - Ohrid : Faculty
of tourism and hospitality, 2025

Начин на пристапување (URL): <https://zenodo.org/communities/inscoses/>
(Слободен пристап). - Наслов преземен од екранот. - Опис на изворот на
ден 26.02.2025. - Библиографија кон трудовите

ISBN 978-608-4676-41-6

а) Туризам -- Собири б) Гастрономија -- Собири в) Економија -- Собири г)
Царина -- Собири

COBISS.MK-ID 65372677

Conference Proceedings INSCOSES
XVII International Scientific Conference on Services Sector INSCOSES, Ohrid,
26-27 September 2024
ISBN 978-608-4676-41-6

UDK 338.48-44-043.86:[334.722.012.63:005.94
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14974257

KNOWLEDGE NETWORKING AS A STRATEGY TO DESTINATION DEVELOPMENT

Branko Nikolovski

University St. Kliment Ohridski, Bitola, North Macedonia
branko.nikolovski@uklo.edu.mk

ABSTRACT

As a service intensive, tourism is a highly complex and multi-sectoral industry. Thus, the interplay comes to forefront between different levels of government, competition, cooperation and stakeholder coordination. Businesses in spatial proximity are considering not their own product only, but also the agglomerate product, the destination itself. Local or spatial concentrated network is defined by series of relationships and collaboration between destination actors. Competitiveness of these actors can be raised by mode of competition and cooperation in the same time based on the following assumptions: first, the tourism industry functions as an umbrella of complementary businesses that collectively offer a composite regional product; second, sustainability demands local coordination and collaboration. Within this cluster structure, knowledge interactions leading to innovation stress the relevance of local and tacit knowledge as an important element within the economic models of regional development. Networking as an informal social mechanism can be relevant to small businesses where knowledge-sharing processes and building inter-organizational relations are viewed as critical for contributing to a destination competitiveness.

KEY WORDS: tourism destinations, networks, knowledge diffusion, entrepreneurship.

INTRODUCTION

Destination level competitive advantage is achieved by building a strategy that covers critical dimensions: how we will develop the business; what goal exactly we will follow; and what policies will be implemented to achieve that goal. Tourism market shelves contain composite products (Mak, 2003). Tourists instead of buying products, are buying "experience" (Horner &

Swarbrooke, 2021). Due to that phenomenon, the attractiveness of a destination is viewed as an amalgamation of tourism attributes that offer integrated experiences and memories. Providing such a smooth experience to the tourists requires building alliances and substantial collaboration between various local actors. As Edgell (1990: 7) point out, ‘. . . there is no other industry in the economy that is linked to so many diverse and different kinds of products and services as the tourism industry’. Tourism players are highly tied to other social, political and economic agents of the local regions within which the local tourism industry is functioning. As a consequence tourism has to be included in the broader regional development, which can be achieved through agent networking, spatial clustering and fostering sustainable innovative process. Innovativeness highlights the tourism destination uniqueness (differentiation) that is not owned by other concurrent regions (Jun, 2016). In this sense, innovation becomes crucial for building competitiveness, and as such, leads as to understanding of how destinations source, share and use knowledge within destination layers.

DESTINATION AS A SYSTEM OF INTERRELATED COMPONENTS

A tourist destination is an example of network activity between various tourism producers. Tourism businesses are run in social contexts where networks of relationships are used in developing collective produced products. The problem arises in defining functioning organization model for such collaboration. Application of social network analysis technique reveals destinations as complex dynamic systems of interrelated components, consisting of formal and informal collaboration, partnerships and networks. A social network will result from linkages among group members, whereas characteristics of these network linkages can be used to visualize behavior of the included persons (Goffi & Cucculelli, 2014). Social networking promotes group collaboration, vertical-horizontal flow of information, and group integration within strategic initiatives (Jamal, 2006). From a destination point of view, the entrepreneurs involved in the destination have different motives and values that affect their business decisions. This reflects the spatial fixity of a tourist product which is designed by these different entrepreneurs, each one dependent on the others to provide unique and unified tourist product. Here, relationship between cooperation and competition comes in its significance with regard to the destination marketing which occurs at all levels (Wang & Krakover, 2008). Viewing the tourist destination as a set of integrated facilities and experiences underlines the necessity of creating tourism clusters as a simplest way to create organized offering of composite

products. Rosenfeld (1998) defines clusters as ‘a geographically bounded concentration of similar, related or complementary businesses, with active channels for business transactions, communications and dialogue, that share specialized infrastructure, labor markets and services, and that are faced with common opportunities and threats.

Local or spatial concentrated network is defined by series of relationships and collaboration between destination actors. Competitiveness of these actors can be raised by mode of competition and cooperation in the same time based on the following assumptions: first, the tourism industry functions as an umbrella of complementary businesses that collectively offer a composite regional product; second, sustainability demands local coordination and collaboration. Additionally, niche logic requires local coordination and embedment into wider products and marketing offerings. As per Porter (1988) competitive advantage can be achieved through localization of supply. In building niche strategy innovation comes at forefront for two reasons: first, for businesses competition and cooperation at macro level in developing complementary products, second, for consideration of the role of the government in developing infrastructure for innovation. In this sense, networks will connect businesses, authorities, interested stakeholders and organizations.

MAPPING STAKEHOLDERS AND DESTINATION COMMUNITY ACTIVISM

Stakeholder theory underlines the relationships of an organization between employees, clients, suppliers, government entities and communities. Whoever has an interest in achieving organization goals, can be qualified as a stakeholder (Morrison, 2018). This leads to the notion of participative government and inviting community activism (Roxas, Rivera, Gutierrez, 2020). Not all stakeholders are equal, considering their individual characteristics and network impact. Stakeholder analysis will reveal key, primary, and secondary stakeholders in an organization. The relative place of a stakeholder is defined by its impact on the creation and dissemination of information in policy network structures.

MODELLING KNOWLEDGE FLOWS IN DESTINATION NETWORK

Productivity, economic growth and innovation are all affected by knowledge and information flows in the destination system (McLeod, 2020). Individual

actors will perform and plan their actions depending on destination success to share knowledge and innovate. Here two main issues arise: first, individual knowledge acquisition mechanisms (firm, group); and, second, dissemination within destination cluster network. Destination networks can be formed by stakeholders based on their similarity or spatiality. Socially dense networks favors search opportunities and experience sharing in turbulent environments, which has overall effect on the local community development. Here we use the term ‘network’ to highlight inter-destination relations based on situated nature of learning and knowledge flows (Pyo, 2005).

COLLABORATIVE KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER

As a service intensive tourism is highly complex and multi-sectoral industry (Moyle, Moyle, & Becken, 2017). Thus, the interplay comes to forefront between different levels of government, competition, cooperation and stakeholder coordination. Businesses in spatial proximity are considering not their own product only, but also the agglomerate product, the destination itself (Adachi, 2018). Collaboration comes naturally in tourism marketing but lacks systemic support from the policy makers. Since publishing of Porter seminal work on competitive advantage of nations (1990) the cluster concept has great impact in the academic field and on policy makers because offers the insight into dynamic processes in the business field. Here collaboration among businesses offers competitive advantage for destination as a whole and for individual business operators. Also, in face of an international competition, local businesses can pool key resources thanks to the processes of collective learning and knowledge sharing. OECD report (Möhring, 2005) underlines the clustering which leads to job creation, better business support and skills acquisition. Horizontal and vertical interdependence of the actors leads to agglomeration of relations between businesses and institutions, to cooperation between different government levels and to coordination in different policy areas.

Some of the authors use the notion of ‘local realities’ when describing clusters and the importance of spatiality, shared values and context of business operations (Goglio, 2002). In these ‘local realities’ there is a high concentration of small businesses specialized in specific attribute of the destination product, local community is highly engaged in the destination production process, and small business dominates the destination development and economy. These small businesses are not owned by some

large conglomerate, are independent of each other, and in the same time create competing and complementary products.

DEVELOPING CLUSTERS THROUGH DESTINATION NETWORKING

Tremblay (1998) proposed a possible local (diagonal) destination network for small business collaboration, it builds on the coordination on the competitive advantage and complementary assets on a destination level. Cooperative marketing play a significant role in this local destination networks. The businesses share public infrastructure, cooperatively manage their resources and innovate on a common basis. Information and communication technology based destination portals make possible diagonal integration and local coordination in value creation. These portals serve as a business entry points that can facilitate customer relations and knowledge sharing through value chain management.

Destination businesses can participate in the network depending on their required economy of scale or the transaction costs goals. These leads to growth and specialization of the small destination cluster based on communication and networking, knowledge sharing, community activism, and value based creation (Braun, 2005).

The literature on destination competitiveness (Rheeders, 2022) has underlined the scenery, climate and accommodation as a key factors of attracting visitors. Clustering is focused on geographical landmarks which provides opportunities for investment returns in underdeveloped areas.

Also, we can identify some barriers to destination clustering (Dias-Sardinha, Ross, & Calapez Gomes, 2017). Many destinations lack the required critical infrastructure (Lóránt Dávid et Csaba Szűcs, 2009) or critical mass of businesses, which is needed for growth and development. As growth and success of a destination and the small businesses are closely intertwined, small businesses tends to cooperation rather than competition in forming value added networks in product creation. But small businesses do not proactively engage in networking, micro operators consider themselves to be lifestyle entrepreneurs. Other barriers are related to the cultural factors and lack of staff, opportunities, time, etc. Small operators are focused mostly on place, network cohesion and branding as determinants for clustering Oerlemans, & Meeus, & Boekema, 2001).

In considering the effects of interaction between the tourism industry and the destination, we need to further investigate the merits of the tourism. Tourism is largely unregulated industry, thus entrepreneurs enter the industry with a low skill base. Low entry barriers and high business failures impact the destination value chain as a whole, the tourism product is the result of multiple operators, not a single one. Since the value is created within the destination, and is matching the required visitor experiences, in turn contributes to positive destination clustering and development. How visitors experience the destination is cumulatively impacted by all value chain participants. One operator who is offering low quality product affects the destination as a whole.

CONCLUSIONS

Networking as an informal social mechanism can be relevant to small businesses where knowledge-sharing processes and building inter-organizational relations are viewed as critical for contributing to a destination competitiveness. Knowledge interactions leading to innovation stress the relevance of local and tacit knowledge as an important element within the economic models of regional development. This leads us to model of clusters described in management studies by Porter (1998), as an agglomeration of interconnected businesses in the same industry in a specific territory. Agglomeration is characterized by the dominance of the primary industry that pervades the destination community to such an extent that can be viewed as an organized enlarged family structure. Within this structure, small businesses are important knowledge intermediaries, as they stage the shelves with tourist experiences. Thus viewing the tourist destination as a set of integrated facilities and experiences underlines the necessity of creating tourism clusters as a simplest way to create organized offering of composite products. Clustering leads to job creation, better business support and skills acquisition. Horizontal and vertical interdependence of the actors leads to agglomeration of relations between businesses and institutions, to cooperation between different government levels and to coordination in different policy areas. Destination businesses can participate in the network depending on their required economy of scale or the transaction costs goals. These leads to growth and specialization based on communication and networking, knowledge sharing, community activism, and value based creation.

REFERENCES:

- Adachi, Y. (2018). Applicability of agglomeration to tourism economics. *Japan and the World Economy*, Elsevier, vol. 47(C), pp. 58-67.
- Braun, P. (2005). Creating value to tourism products through tourism networks and clusters: uncovering destination value chains. In: *Proceedings of the OECD-Korea international tourism conference global tourism growth: a challenge for SMEs*, pp. 6–7
- Dias-Sardinha, I., Ross, D., & Calapez Gomes, A. (2017). The clustering conditions for managing creative tourism destinations: the Alqueva region case, Portugal. *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management*, 61(4), pp. 635–655
- Edgell, D. L. (1990). *International Tourism Policy*. Van Nostrand Reinhold
- Goffi, G. & Cucculelli, M. (2014). Components of Destination Competitiveness. The case of Small Tourism Destinations in Italy. *International Journal of Tourism Policy*, 5, pp. 296 - 326
- Goglio, S. (2002). Introduction: The Industrial District as a Proving Ground. *European Planning Studies*, 10(4), pp. 421–424.
- Horner, S., Swarbrooke, J. (2021). *Consumer Behaviour in Tourism*. Routledge/Taylor & Francis Group
- Jamal, T. (2006). Collaborative Networks and Partnerships for Integrated Destination Management. In book: *Tourism Management Dynamics*, pp. 164-172
- Jun, K. S. (2016). The structural relationships of destination image, awareness, uniqueness and destination loyalty in periurban ecotourism destination. *EJTHR*; 7(3), pp. 212-225
- Lóránt Dávid et Csaba Szűcs. (2009). Building of networking, clusters and regions for tourism in the Carpathian Basin via Information and Communication Technologies. *Netcom*, 23-1/2, pp. 63-74.
- Mak, J. (2003). *Tourism and the economy: Understanding the economics of tourism*. University of Hawaii Press.
- McLeod, M. (2020). Understanding knowledge flows within a tourism destination network. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Insights*, vol. 3, no. 5, pp. 549-566.
- Möhring, J. (Ed.). (2005). *Business clusters: promoting enterprise in Central and Eastern Europe*. OECD Publishing.
- Morrison, A. M. (2018). Destination community and stakeholder relationships and involvement. In book: *Marketing and Managing Tourism Destinations*.

-
- Moyle, C. Lee J., Moyle, B. D., & Becken, S. (2017). A multi-sectoral model of tourism and resource sector transformation. *Tourism Recreation Research*, 42(4), pp. 422–435.
- Oerlemans, L. & Meeus, M. & Boekema, F. (2001). Firm Clustering and Innovation: Determinants and Effects. *Papers in Regional Science*, 80, pp. 337-356
- Porter, M. E. (1988). *Competitive Advantage*. Free Press
- Porter, M. E. (1990). *The Competitive Advantage of Nations*. New York: Free Press
- Pyo, S. (2005). Knowledge map for tourist destinations—needs and implications. *Tourism Management*, vol. 26, Iss. 4, pp. 583-594
- Rheeders, T. (2022). A review of the determinants of tourism destination competitiveness. *Journal of Contemporary Management*, 19, pp. 238-268
- Rosenfeld, S. A. (1998). Exports, competitiveness, and synergy in Appalachian industry clusters. A report to the Appalachian Regional Commission. Diane Publishing Co, Darby, <https://arc.gov/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/ExportsCompetitivenessandSynergyinAppalachia.pdf>
- Roxas, F. M. Y., Rivera, J. P. R., Gutierrez, E. L. M. (2020). Mapping stakeholders' roles in governing sustainable tourism destinations. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*, vol. 45, pp. 387-398
- Tremblay, P. (1998). The economic organization of tourism. *Annals of Tourism Research*, vol. 25, iss.4, pp. 837-859
- Wang, Y., Krakover, Sh. (2008). Destination marketing: competition, cooperation or co-competition? *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, vol. 20, iss. 2, pp. 126-141